

APÉNDICE

LIST OF CONTENTS FROM THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Content sections	Questions
AI applications in school counseling	Which tasks within your work could benefit from AI?
	How do you think AI can influence students' decision-making autonomy in vocational guidance?
	What uses of AI do you consider can help address diversity in school counseling?
Challenges associated with the implementation of AI in school counseling	What recommendations are necessary to ensure the ethical use of AI tools in school counseling?
	What aspects should be considered to maintain a human and empathetic connection in this technological context?
	How do you think AI might affect the relationship between the school counselor and the student?
	What improvements do you think AI can bring to student learning?
Training needs and role of the school counselors in AI environments	What controversies can be expected from incorporating AI in school counseling?
	How do you envision your role as a counselor with AI playing a central role?
	Do you think your professional responsibilities will change with the use of AI?
	What type of training do you consider essential for the effective use of AI in school counseling?